

Template - Code Smells Refactoring in OSS Projects

Class:

Team:

Project:

I'm currently working on refactoring the following code smell:

My main difficulties in removing these anomalies are:

I am using the following refactoring methods to remove code smells:

When refactoring this smell, I realized that the following code smells are inserted or not:

When refactoring this smell, I realized that there was an improvement or not in the following quality metrics:

Enter the average amount of time it took to refactor the code smell: